

How does OPeNDAP learn about its users?

Conferences

Approach: We interviewed people at conferences and meetings relevant to OPeNDAP's topic area, asking:

- Have you ever heard of OPeNDAP?
- Have you ever used OPeNDAP?
- What did you use OPeNDAP for?
- How did you learn to use OPeNDAP?

Audience: People in Earth Science.

Sample size: 159 (started in July 2023)

Strengths: Provides quality data with tailored questions.

Weaknesses: Time consuming, resource intensive, populations at meetings are often homogeneous.

OPeNDAP support email

Approach: OPeNDAP users write to support@opendap.org when they need help. Data are scraped from the emails and analyzed.

Audience: People using OPeNDAP.

Sample size: 443 (Jan 2019-Dec 2024)

Strengths: No effort needed for data collection, so a high data volume about users is possible.

Weaknesses: Information quality is difficult to control and often incomplete.

Online survey

Approach: An online survey is easily shared. Currently being tested on the OPeNDAP website.

Audience: People with a strong interest in OPeNDAP.

Sample size: ~10 (started in Oct 2024)

Strengths: Provides quality data with tailored questions and minimal effort.

Weaknesses: People often don't fill out surveys without strong encouragement.

Website analytics

Approach: Use Google analytics to collect UX/UI data from people who visit OPeNDAP-supported websites.

Audience: People with interest in OPeNDAP.

Sample size: ~1000 per month

Strengths: Little effort needed for data collection or analysis, so a high data volume is possible.

Weaknesses: Limited to collecting observational data on people's behavior using the website's content.

Tips to Plan Your Own User Research Program

- ❖ **Define the questions you want to answer**
- ❖ **Identify opportunities for learning about your audiences**
 - In what ways do you already interact with your audiences?
 - Are there new ways that you want to interact with your users?
- ❖ **Identify your audiences**
 - Each opportunity for learning targets different audiences, so aim to diversify which opportunities you use.
 - Collect demographic data so you can track if you are reaching your target audiences.
- ❖ **Identify the resources you have available**
 - Who is able to collect data and analyze it? Plan for about 3x as much effort to analyze/reflect upon the data as it does to collect it.
- ❖ **Be systematic**
 - Start with loose exploratory work to identify the right questions (what will elicit the information you want?), and then move to more structured questions and data collection templates as you hone in on what's working well.
 - Develop habits to bring your learnings into strategic decision making. This can be as simple as discussing findings at meetings on a regular basis or giving annual presentations.

OPeNDAP

www.opendap.org

About OPeNDAP: Established as a nonprofit in 2000, OPeNDAP is the developer of the OPeNDAP client/server software. DAP = "Data Access Protocol" is a data transmission protocol originally designed by OPeNDAP. Hyrax is the server half of OPeNDAP.

Information based on: Virapongse, A., J. Gallagher (2024) Multidisciplinary Use of Earth Science Data: An Analysis of OPeNDAP Users [SY21C-2443]. American Geophysical Union 2024, Washington D.C., December 9-13.

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